

EIRENE PPP

D1.2 – EIRENE RI Architecture WP1 – Scientific Vision & Technical Implementation

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EIRENE Architecture

The EIRENE RI project proposal aimed at filling the gap between environmental exposures and human health and developing main infrastructural components of the human exposome research (shown in Fig. 1). In the heart of it are novel capacities for an assessment of chemical exposures. Mass spectroscopy techniques combined with liquid and gas chromatographic separations can serve not only for the identification and quantification of exogenous compounds indicating chemical exposures but also endogenous chemicals as markers of biological effects of such exposures. High-resolution applications can be also used a suspect screening and non-target characterisation of biological samples. An exposure assessment must be complemented with an assessment of hazards enabling the translation of exposures to health risks.

A close collaboration with infrastructures operating in the environmental (ACTRIS, ICOS, ANAEE), health and food (ECRIN, BBMRI, EATRIS, METROFOOD, ELIXIR), and social (SHARE, GUIDE, GGP) domains was expected to link data on chemical risks with those on environmental and social conditions, and on population health. Data storage and computing capacities will be secured through a collaboration with e-infrastructures. The synergies with the European Open Science will be identified and strengthened to ensure an adoption of the FAIR principles.

Figure 1: EIRENE Structure scheme from the original application

During the EIRENE PPP implementation, a detailed analysis of existing national, European, and global infrastructural capacities and their gaps was complemented by consultations with various stakeholders including funders and potential users of the EIRENE RI. This resulted in the new EIRENE structure (Figure 2) where all services are organized around six pillars. These services are described in a more detail in Table 1. In the first three pillars (chemical, toxicological and biological profiling), the users will get an access – both physical (secondments) and remote (analytical services) to the laboratory capacities available in the EIRENE national nodes. The last three pillars are focused on enhanced accessibility of data and data processing tools. However, they offer not only an access to available data but – in cases when data is not available yet – an access to the biobanked samples or even the monitoring/biomonitoring programmes generating such samples.

Pillars	Access mode			Domain	EIRENE services classification
	Physical	Remote	Virtual		
A Chemical profiling	✓	✓		Laboratory capacities for chemical profiling (selective / non-selective data acquisition)	(Target/non-target) measurement of exogenous substances (parent compound and transformation products) and their mixtures in the environment and human biofluids and tissues
B Toxicological profiling	✓	✓		Laboratory capacities for hazard assessment (non-animal toxicological models to test toxicity of chemicals, their mixtures & environmental samples)	Quantification/determination of toxicity (human and eco-adverse outcome pathways and modes of action in-vivo, ex-vivo, in-vitro, in-silico)
C Biological Profiling	✓	✓		Laboratory capacities for biological profiling (elucidating the impact of toxic exposures on health)	Omics-based markers of biological response (both MS-based and sequencing technologies), e.g., (epi)genomics, transcriptomics, metagenomics/microbiomics, proteomics, metabolomics, lipidomics, adductomics
D Environmental data & samples		✓	✓	Data from large-scale longitudinal environmental (air, indoor, soil, food, consumer products – on-site, remote, satellite) monitoring for assessing the external exposome	Databases and portals presenting environmental (pollutants, temperature, noise), exposure maps, and other tools that can be further combined with socioeconomic and/or lifestyle data Biobanked samples enabling delivery of such data Access to monitoring networks enabling collection of such data/samples
E Human data & samples		✓	✓	Data from longitudinal population cohorts covering various groups, cross-sectional studies, health surveys, and clinical studies as an information source on population exposure and health	Databases and portals presenting human environmental (chemical biomonitoring, temperature, noise) and socioeconomic exposure, behaviour, lifestyle, and health data Biobanked samples enabling delivery of such data Access to population studies enabling collection of such data/samples
F Tools		✓	✓	Data management, processing, federated analysis, modeling, and presentation tools and platforms, computational capacities and virtual laboratories	Fair cataloguing of exposome data (e.g., cohorts, algorithms) Biostatistical and/or bioinformatics tools and platforms for investigating exposome-human health interactions

Table 1: EIRENE service pillars

In addition to services provided by the national nodes, there will be specific functions of the coordination hub. They include especially the harmonisation and quality assurance/quality control measures necessary to assure a compliance with the open science principles, transparency, and a highest quality of provided services and data (including providing experimental/data/metadata standards, harmonization and QA/QC procedures). The central hub will also coordinate trans-national (physical and remote) and virtual accesses to distributed capacities of national nodes, run the open access system with user support services, and communicate with users and responsible bodies. Education (training for both, operators and users) and communication (continuous stakeholders consultations and outreach) will be also managed centrally.

Figure 2: Preliminary EIRENE architecture

Functionalities of the EIRENE open-access system will be tested in the EIRENE pilot designed already within the EIRENE PPP project but initiated in the implementation period. The open-access procedures to be tested were described in D4,1, and the EIRENE RI facilities and their services to be included in the Pilot were selected in D4.2. These deliverables provided an input for the preliminary roadmap for the development of EIRENE RI services (D2.2) which is a living document that will be continuously updated with every set of new services added in the implementation period.

During the preparatory phase, EIRENE benefits from synergies with the Horizon Europe Partnership for Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC), the Horizon 2020 European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) and the Horizon Europe International Human Exposome Network project.

The PARC Partnership develops tools for exposure, hazard and risk assessment to deliver data for improved policy making and better protection of human and environmental health from the chemical exposures. However, it also has two specific work packages focused on the systematic development of infrastructural and human capacities, including data management capacities in line with the FAIR principles. The goal of the work packages is to provide an inventory of existing and newly developed capacities, assess their quality, contribute to their visibility and long-term sustainability. Therefore, the EIRENE RI is one of important elements of the PARC sustainability strategy as it can assure that data and tools developed in the project will be available to policy makers after the PARC implementation (2029). The PARC input will be very important for the development of the EIRENE catalogue

of services, harmonization and QA/QC procedures but also for future enhancement of services in all six pillars.

Figure 3: Interactions with the PARC Partnership

There are also important synergies between EIRENE and the International Human Exposome Network established in 2024 as the CSA project under the Horizon Europe. The goal of the project is to establish a global exposome community and jointly develop a roadmap for future human exposome research and its integration into the biomedical and clinical domains. IHEN will provide an access to the global exposome research communities well as an important input for the EIRENE long-term research and development strategy to reflect the current state of the art. IHEN is based on former EHEN projects and as such, it also provides a unique platform integrating knowledge, data and tools developed in these projects. There will be an on-going discussion on further enhancement of EIRENE services and capacities to support future exposome projects.

Figure 4: Interactions with the International Human Exposome Network (IHEN)

It should be also mentioned that the National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences will invest in the synergistic human exposome-related activities in the US within their NEXUS programme. As the EIRENE RI has a global ambition and the US node was among the founding members of this infrastructure, the EIRENE structure design will be continuously updated throughout the EIRENE RI preparatory project to adapt to emerging scientific and societal challenges and global priorities.